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**AN APPRAISAL OF INFERTILITY DISCOURSE ON SELECTED HEALTH
NARRATIVES ON *OMO FRANCA'S* BLOG**

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Abstract

This study investigates aspects of evaluative meaning in the infertility discourse of selected health narratives on *Omo Franca's Blog* (my baby testimony blogspot) using Martin and White's (2005) Appraisal Theory as the analytical framework. The study adopts a qualitative research design, drawing its primary data from twenty-four purposively selected infertility narratives posted between 2008 and 2015. The analysis focuses on how linguistic resources of attitude, engagement, and graduation were deployed by narrators to construct evaluative meanings, negotiate interpersonal relationships, and express affective, judgmental, and appreciative stances toward their infertility experiences. The study uncovers how linguistic resources are employed by narrators to express emotion, negotiate interpersonal positions and construe attitudes towards infertility experiences. Findings reveal that the attitudinal subsystem, particularly the affect and judgment components, dominates the narratives, reflecting the narrators' emotional turmoil, social struggles, and moral positioning within a culturally sensitive and stigmatizing context. The engagement subsystem is employed to align or disalign with social voices, while graduation amplifies the emotional intensity and social evaluation of infertility experiences. Linguistically, these evaluative resources achieve empathy, solidarity, and identity reconstruction, allowing narrators to reframe personal suffering into resilience and agency. *The study contributes to discourse-analytic scholarship by foregrounding how appraisal resources shape meaning, emotion, and social positioning in digital health narratives within the Nigerian sociocultural context.*

Keywords: affect, appraisal theory, attitude, discourse analysis, evaluative meaning, Infertility discourse, judgment, Omo Franca's blog,

Introduction

Discourse analysis is a field of linguistics that investigates how language functions within social contexts to construct meaning, identity, and power relations. Discourse analysis is the study of language in use, examining how spoken and written communication shapes and reflects social realities (Brown & Yule 1983). It goes beyond the study of isolated linguistic structures to examine how communication reflects and shapes human realities. A significant branch of this field is medical discourse, which focuses on the language surrounding health, illnesses, and treatments. Within this, infertility discourse constitutes a specific and sensitive domain, concerned with how the experience of infertility is communicated and understood. Medical discourse studies typically focus on doctor–patient interactions, consultation patterns, health advertisements, and narratives surrounding illness and recovery (Coulthard & Ashby, 1976; Labov & Fanshel, 1977; Adegbite, 1991; Odebunmi, 2006). These analyses highlight how linguistic choices influence both interpersonal relationships and social attitudes toward health conditions.

A specific dimension of medical discourse is infertility discourse, which holds deep cultural and emotional significance, particularly in societies where childbearing is central to marital fulfillment and social status. The World Health Organization (2009) defines infertility as the inability of a couple to conceive after twelve months of unprotected sexual intercourse. In Nigeria, infertility often carries heavy stigma, resulting in psychological distress, marital tension, and social exclusion (Orji, 2008). Such realities are frequently reflected in how infertility is discussed across different communicative platforms (from traditional street hawking of herbal remedies to broadcast and print media campaigns) and more recently, digital platforms such as blogs and social media (Olateju, 2009). These discourses, whether oral, written, or digital, reveal society’s values, beliefs, and anxieties about fertility, gender, and identity.

The emergence of online health narratives has expanded the space for discussing infertility, allowing sufferers to share personal experiences, seek support, and challenge cultural taboos. Blogs such as *Omo Franca's* provide intimate accounts of infertility, offering insights into the emotional and evaluative dimensions of this discourse. Despite growing interests in medical discourse, infertility discourse (especially as expressed in digital health narratives) remains underexplored in Nigerian linguistic scholarship. Previous studies have applied frameworks such as pragmatics, conversation analysis, and discourse analysis (Adegbite & Odebunmi, 2006; Taiwo & Salami, 2007; Abioye, 2011), but few have examined the evaluative meanings embedded in infertility narratives through the lens of appraisal theory.

This study therefore investigates aspects of evaluative meaning in infertility discourse on Omo Franca's blog, focusing on how language conveys the three components of Martin and White's (2005) appraisal theory (attitude, engagement, and graduation) in the narratives of those experiencing infertility. By analyzing the appraisal resources in these narratives, the research connects linguistic choices to human realities by illustrating how individuals construct resilience, negotiate identity, and express emotional responses to one of life's most sensitive challenges.

The study seeks to uncover how narrators show how the discourse of infertility generates emotions, negotiate stances, judge human behavior and reveal the cultural importance and expectations placed on fertility deploy linguistic resources. Therefore, the study intends to provide answers to the following questions

a).what are the linguistic resources used in encoding evaluative meanings in the selected infertility narratives on *Omo Franca's blog*?

- b). how are the three subsystems of Appraisal Theory (Attitude, Engagement and Graduation) realized in the infertility narratives?
- c). what are the interpersonal meanings conveyed through the narrators 'evaluative choices in representing infertility experiences?
- d). which of the subsystem(s) of appraisal theory dominate(s) the infertility narratives? and explain how narrators construct identities, negotiate social solidarity and manage stigma surrounding infertility.

Literature Review

Adegbite and Odebunmi (2006) investigated the discourse tactics employed in doctor–patient interactions during diagnoses in English within Southwestern Nigerian hospitals. Drawing on recorded conversations and interviews from thirty hospitals, their study employs mutual contextual beliefs and speech act theory to analyse interactional patterns. Findings reveal that opening and supporting moves dominate diagnostic discourse, while challenge moves are rare. Doctors typically initiate interactions to elicit or confirm information and give directives. The study also finds that violations of conversational maxims (except the maxim of quantity) reflect participants' beliefs about emotional expression and compassion. Face acts in these exchanges further demonstrate the influence of cultural attitudes on communicative behaviour.

In a related study, Odebunmi (2006) examines the pragmatic roles of locutionary acts in medical discourse, focusing on how doctors and patients use language to negotiate meanings. Using tape-recorded interactions and interviews from hospitals across Southwestern Nigeria, the research categorises hospital discourse into two locution types: those intended for non-professional understanding and those restricted to professional circles. When clarity is required, doctors employ

explicit language that aligns with patients' lexical competence, reflecting adherence to the Gricean maxim of manner. Conversely, medical practitioners use coded or slang expressions to conceal sensitive discussions from patients. The study also distinguishes between standard global medical lexical items and local innovations adapted for pragmatic effectiveness within Nigerian hospital contexts.

Taiwo and Salami (2007) explore discourse organisation and acts in antenatal classroom interactions to assess how language influences expectant mothers' comprehension and behavioural outcomes. Based on recordings from twenty antenatal classes in Ile-Ife, the study identifies a teacher-dominated discourse structure, where educators exercise communicative authority and pregnant women assume passive, listener roles. The antenatal sessions mirror traditional classroom hierarchies, emphasising information transmission over interactions. The researchers argue that this power imbalance limits comprehension and engagement, recommending a more dialogic, interactive approach to antenatal education that fosters participation and practical learning for expectant mothers.

Abioye (2011) analyses discourse patterns between nurses and mothers in Child Welfare Clinics (CWCs) in Southwestern Nigeria to understand how language shapes relationships and communication effectiveness. Using recordings and transcriptions of clinic interactions, the study reveals that multilingual communication through posters, stickers, and oral interactions plays a crucial role in disseminating health information. However, since some audience members are illiterate, they rely solely on oral communication from nurses. Abioye stresses the need for nurses to monitor language translations—especially into indigenous languages like Yoruba—to ensure accurate message delivery. The study highlights that effective medical communication depends on context-sensitive linguistic adaptation and clarity of message transmission.

Odebunmi (2013) focuses on culture-constrained politeness cues in hospital consultations, examining hundred (100) recorded sessions from twenty-five (25) hospitals in Southwestern Nigeria. The study analyses how greetings and politeness strategies reflect Yoruba cultural norms and institutional hierarchies. Findings show that politeness cues in doctor–patient exchanges create both interactive alignments and disalignments depending on greeting structures (adjacency or non-adjacency pairs). Partial alignments occur when greetings mutually acknowledge face needs, while disalignments arise when Western institutional norms override Yoruba expectations of respect. Doctors’ institutional authority often suppresses patients’ responses, yet patients pragmatically accommodate such asymmetries. The study concludes that politeness in medical interactions is shaped by both local cultural practices and the institutional power dynamics of healthcare.

These studies demonstrate that medical discourse in Nigeria is marked by hierarchical structures, pragmatic adaptations, and culturally influenced communicative norms. Adebite and Odebunmi (2006) and Odebunmi (2006) foreground the interactional and pragmatic dimensions of doctor–patient talk, while Taiwo and Salami (2007) highlight pedagogical dominance in antenatal discourse. Abioye (2011) emphasises linguistic accessibility and translation accuracy, and Odebunmi (2013) focuses on politeness and cultural negotiation in consultations.

Despite these contributions, the existing research largely centres on professional–patient communication and institutional settings. The language of sufferers themselves (particularly those expressing personal experiences of medical conditions such as infertility) remains underexplored. This current study extends the discourse inquiry to infertility narratives, analysing how individuals linguistically construct emotion, resilience, and evaluative meaning within online health communication contexts.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored in Martin and White's Appraisal Theory (2005), a framework within Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) that systematizes the analysis of interpersonal meanings in discourse. Appraisal theory investigates the subjective presence of text producers and their stances toward discourse participants and propositions. The theory helps writers and speakers to know that whenever they speak or write, they are not just giving information but also showing emotions and building relationships. It is organized into three major semantic systems: Attitude, Engagement, and Graduation (Martin and White 2005).

Attitude encompasses emotional responses (affect), moral evaluations of behavior (judgment), and aesthetic assessments of entities or processes (appreciation) (Bednarek, 2006 ; Martin and White, 2005).

Engagement involves the ways speakers or writers position themselves and others through linguistic resources such as projection, modality, polarity, and concession, thereby acknowledging or denying various viewpoints (Martin and White, 2005).

Graduation refers to the scaling or intensity of evaluations, determining how strongly emotions or judgments are expressed and how sharply categories are defined (Bednarek, 2006).

This framework enables a detailed analysis of the evaluative language and stance-taking strategies within infertility narratives, highlighting how narrators construct affective and moral positions through discourse.

Methodology

The study adopts a qualitative research design, employing both primary and secondary data. The primary data consist of twenty-four (24) purposively selected infertility narratives drawn from

Omo Franca's Blog on the website: (www.mybabytestimony.blogspot.com), chosen for its specific focus on infertility issues. Narratives posted between 2008 and 2015 were used, corresponding to the period during which the blogger began featuring infertility-related stories.

Using purposive sampling, narratives were selected for analysis based on their linguistic creativity, richness and evaluative depth; twenty-four (24) narratives that were rich in evaluative meanings were labeled N1–N24. Each narrative underwent close reading to facilitate in-depth analysis. The researcher identified interpersonal components of clauses and examined emotive strategies employed by narrators. Particular attention was given to how lexical and grammatical features were utilized to construct evaluative meanings and interpersonal positioning within the discourse.

Analysis

1. Attitude (Affect, Judgment, Appreciation)

A. Affect (emotion): These are the linguistic resources deployed by narrators to express their feelings (e.g., sorrow, joy, anxiety, relief, gratitude).

Emotion adjectives/adverbials: sorrowful, overwhelmed, joyful, thankful, frightened, worried, jubilant, and ecstatic.

Example: 'I was always in a sorrowful spirit.' (Narrative One).

Mental processes + complements (I felt , I was... , I knew): I felt very worried; I was crying; I knew God was working.

Example: I felt very worried, asking why I should be in this problem...' (Narrative One).

Bodily behaviour as affective evidence (wet my pillow / tears flowed / cried): these are material/behavioural process descriptions that show emotional intensity.

Example: 'I wet my pillow with uncontrollable tears.' (Narrative One).

Exclamative and performative clauses that show feeling: 'I screamed and cried', 'I couldn't contain my joy'.

Example: 'When they told me I was pregnant, I ran a test and it said I was pregnant, I was like truly those that dream. I screamed and cried' (Narrative Eleven).

Emotion metaphors: 'God wiped away my tears', 'God bulldozed barrenness'. (metaphorical phrasing portrays affect as divine action.)

Example: 'God is a barrenness bulldozer'. (Narrative One).

Affect resources establish an emotional journey: suffering - waiting/patience - vindication/joy. Bodily behaviour and strong emotion verbs make the suffering vivid, while exclamatives and gratitude verbs index closure and testimony.

B. Judgment (ethic-moral evaluation of people's behaviour) linguistic resources under judgement are used to evaluate human conduct and character. They are used to evaluate characters as virtuous, culpable, tenacious, shameful etc.

Judgment of capacity and normality through attributes: 'he stood by me', 'he remained steadfast', 'people mocked me', 'they condemned her'. These are mostly attributive relational clauses.

Example: 'My husband was patient and compassionate' (Narrative One).

Verbal reports that attribute action/opinion to others (reporting verbs): they said, people called me, rumoured, accused. These construct social blame or support reportedly rather than directly.

Example: 'It was rumoured that I did not have a womb' (Narrative One).

Moral dichotomies expressed in predication: faithful vs. foolish, patient vs. abusive, supportive vs. mocking. Frequently realized via adjectival attributions and evaluative nouns (e.g., charms, curse).

Example: 'She called me all sorts of names like 'good for nothing woman'. (Narrative One).

Praise of religious/moral virtues (tenacity, faith): 'he refused to patronise false prophets', 'we remained steadfast', 'we waited on the Lord'. These are positive moral judgments which are used to advice readers.

Example: 'My faith in the Lord became strengthened as the day pass by'. (Narrative Two).

Judgment constructs social actors (spouses, in-laws, doctors, pastors) as morally charged figures often placing moral virtue on the narrator and couple and blame and shame on community and /antagonists. Reporting verbs mediate social accusations, softening direct confrontation.

C. Appreciation (evaluation of things, events, acts) linguistic and appreciation resources evaluates phenomena (pregnancy, miracles, testimonies) aesthetically or value-wise.

Evaluative adjectives and nouns: marvellous, wonderful, miraculous, marvelous child, a bundle of joy, joy unspeakable.

Example: 'The Lord has done a marvellous thing that is really wonderful in my life'. (Narrative Four).

Nominalisation of outcomes as gifts or miracles: ‘God gave us Ayomideji’, ‘the arrival of the baby’ framed as divine gift.

Example: ‘God went on to fulfil His promise in their lives by bestowing a bouncing baby girl’. (Narrative Four).

Metaphorical praise (divine agency): ‘God is a winner... God bulldozed barrenness’. These metaphors reframe biomedical failure as a stage for divine intervention.

Appreciation revalues infertility narratives: infertility is reframed as a test, and the birth is aestheticised as miraculous and socially significant (honour, reputation restored).

2. ENGAGEMENT (dialogic positioning; how other voices are admitted, suppressed, or countered)

Engagement shows how narrators position their claims relative to other voices (doctors, family, community, God). Engagement resources produce either monoglossia (asserting single voice) or heteroglossia (acknowledging conflicting voices).

This is mostly realized by the use of reported speeches and reporting clauses: ‘the doctor said...’, ‘they told me...’, ‘he advised us...’ these enable a presentation of authoritative voices (medical, familial, religious). These are central to dialogic contrast (e.g., doctor vs God).

Example: ‘the doctor diagnosed damage in my womb. He said that the damage had resulted in infertility’ (Narrative One).

Concessive structures and adversative conjunctions: ‘but’, ‘yet’, ‘however’, ‘although’, They are used to contrast medical and lay pessimism with faith and hope: doctors said X, but God did Y.

Example: ‘Doctors were still saying the same thing, singing the same old song... yet there was no solution’ (Narrative One):

Modal and epistemic markers to hedge or strengthen claims: ‘I knew’, ‘I believed’, ‘I was sure’, ‘it seemed’. All these locate certainty and commitment.

Example: ‘I was sure that on that day, May 22, God gave me a solid promise’. (Narrative Nine and Ten).

Authoritative religious voices and scriptural citations: ‘the God of Abraham and Sarah’, ‘the foolishness of God is wiser than men’: These intertextual scripture frames voice as divine-authoritative, closing down alternative explanations.

Example: ‘The foolishness of God is wiser than men.’(Narrative One):

Dialogic contraction (i.e., assertive monogloss): Miraculous claims are often presented with no alternate possibility: ‘God did it for me.’ These are monoglossic, exclusionary utterances strengthening testimonial authority.

Example: ‘God is a winner, you will win this battle.’ (Narrative One)

Engagement resources create a rhetorical battle line between medical and scientific voices and religious and testimonial voices. Narrators routinely report opposing medical diagnoses and then close down alternatives by invoking divine interventions, a strategy that both legitimizes the testimony and mobilises the faith community.

3. GRADUATION (force and focus scaling intensity and sharpening/softening categories)

These are linguistic resources that scales evaluation (how intense / how categorical).

Intensifiers & amplifiers (i.e., Force): very, so much, truly, really, infinitely, greatly, uncontrollable, utterly. These escalate both suffering and joy.

Example: ‘My husband loved me so much’ and ‘uncontrollable tears.’ (Narrative One).

Quantifiers & numerals indicating extreme cases: ‘23 years’, ‘18 miscarriages’, ‘30 years’, ‘triplets’, ‘quadruplets’. All these numerical detail increases rhetorical force and credibility (the longer the wait and larger the number, the stronger the miracle).

Example: ‘A MOTHER AT LAST, AFTER 23 YEAR BATTLE WITH BARRENNNESS’.
(Narrative One heading).

Example: ‘18 miscarriages’ (Narrative Five).

Superlatives and absolutes: ‘the greatest’, ‘the most wonderful thing’, ‘abundantly above all that we ask’. These give maximal force to divine action.

Example: ‘God did abundantly above all that we ask’ (Narrative One).

Focus sharpening vs softening: phrases like ‘truly’, ‘indeed’ sharpen evaluative categories; hedges like ‘seemed’, ‘almost’, ‘it was like a dream’ soften claims (often used when a speaker narrates something extraordinary).

Example: ‘It was like a dream. I decided not to go to the hospital...’ (Narrative Nine).

Graduation resources were used to dramatize narratives; the length of waiting (numerals), intensifiers, and superlatives magnify the miracle and enhance testimonial authority. Focus markers manage credibility (a little hedge when the event seems unbelievable, then intensifiers reinforce).

The dominance of Attitude, particularly Affect and Judgment, linguistically achieves the following:

1. Emotional Persuasion and Empathy Building: Through affective language, narrators evoke emotional resonance, drawing the reader into their psychological space.

2. Identity Construction and Resistance: Judgment resources allow narrators to reclaim moral agency and redefine self-worth against stigmatizing cultural norms.

3. Social Critique: Evaluations of others and of institutions expose the inequities and gendered ideologies inherent in Nigerian infertility discourse.

4. Narrative Healing: Expressing emotion through linguistic means becomes a therapeutic act, a way of reconstructing resilience and coherence in fragmented life stories.

It is therefore pertinent to note that Appraisal analysis shows that Attitude dominates the infertility narratives because infertility is a profoundly emotional and identity-threatening experience. Linguistically, this dominance allows narrators to articulate pain, negotiate morality, and reconstruct selfhood in a context of cultural blame and social marginalization.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study examined the linguistic construction of emotions in selected infertility narratives on *Omo Franca's Blog*, using Martin and White's (2005) Appraisal Theory as the analytical framework. The investigation revealed that infertility discourse in Nigeria is deeply emotional, evaluative, and socially situated. Through the deployment of appraisal resources (particularly the Attitude, Engagement, and Graduation subsystems) narrators articulate not only their personal pain but also broader cultural, moral, and spiritual struggles associated with infertility.

Findings show that the Attitude subsystem, especially the Affect and Judgment categories, dominated the discourse. This indicates that narrators largely relied on emotional and moral evaluations to construct their experiences. Words and expressions such as ‘I felt empty and less of a woman (narrative one), ‘my heart bled each time I saw a pregnant woman ,’ and “I cried endlessly” reveal profound sadness, despair, and social alienation. These linguistic choices foreground the emotional turbulence that accompanies infertility, demonstrating how language becomes a means of externalizing inner pain and seeking empathy from readers. Similarly, positive affective expressions such as “hope kept me alive despite the mockery” and “God’s timing is perfect” reflect optimism, faith, and psychological resilience. Through such linguistic acts, narrators transform suffering into hope, constructing a discourse of endurance and divine trust.

The Judgment subsystem further revealed how narrators evaluated human behavior, often condemning societal stigma, insensitive medical treatment, or moral judgment from others. Statements like ‘People called me barren as if it was my fault’ and ‘My mother-in-law said I was a curse to the family’ expose the social cruelty and gendered blame embedded in Nigerian infertility discourse. In contrast, narrators’ self-evaluations such as ‘I remained faithful even when my husband took another wife’ reflect moral strength, patience, and virtue, which serve to restore dignity and agency within oppressive social structures.

Additionally, Engagement resources revealed how narrators dialogically positioned themselves in relation to societal, medical, and spiritual voices. Phrases like ‘They said I was bewitched, but I knew it was not spiritual’ and ‘The doctor told me I could never conceive, yet here I am with twins’ show resistance to dominant ideologies and reassertion of personal belief systems. Meanwhile, Graduation resources amplified emotional intensity, emphasizing the depth of pain (‘It was the

worst moment of my life’) and the magnitude of joy (‘Only God could understand my pain’) upon eventual conception.

Overall, the linguistic patterns across the narratives demonstrate that infertility discourse is both a site of pain and empowerment. The narrators’ emotional expressions function as discursive therapy, transforming personal suffering into shared experience, solidarity, and spiritual affirmation. By evaluating their experiences through affective, moral, and ideological lenses, these narrators reclaim agency over a stigmatized identity and redefine womanhood beyond biological reproduction.

Conclusion

This study affirms that the appraisal of infertility narratives reveals much more than individual grief, it exposes the socio-cultural ideologies that shape reproductive identity and gender expectations in Nigeria. It also highlights the transformative power of language in expressing emotion, constructing resilience, and challenging stigma. Infertility, as reflected in these narratives, becomes not just a medical condition but a linguistic and emotional journey a testament to human endurance, faith, and the reassertion of self through evaluative discourse.

This study contributes to knowledge in the fields of Discourse Analysis, Appraisal Linguistics, and Health Communication by providing fresh insights into how language functions as a tool for emotional expression, identity reconstruction, and social resistance within infertility discourse in Nigeria. While previous studies on infertility have focused largely on medical, psychological, or sociological dimensions, this research foregrounds the linguistic realization of emotion as a means through which individuals negotiate meaning, self-worth, and resilience in a stigmatizing socio-cultural context.

This study advances existing scholarship by demonstrating that emotion in infertility discourse is linguistically performative it does not merely describe suffering but constructs identity, negotiates stigma, and manifests resilience. Through the integration of Critical Discourse Analysis and Appraisal Theory, the research enriches the understanding of how individuals use language to transform private anguish into collective strength, thereby adding a novel dimension to the study of emotion and discourse in reproductive health narratives.

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